

AVIAN DIVERSITY AND SPECIES RICHNESS OF WETLAND AREAS IN JABALPUR

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MS Received: 27.06.2025; MS Revised: 28.07.2025; MS Accepted: 29.07.2025

MS 3440/1

(RESEARCH PAPER IN WILDLIFE FORENSIC AND HEALTH)

Abstract:

The Narmada valley in Jabalpur supports a number of wetlands in Madhya Pradesh, which serve as ideal habitats for dependent species. Human encroachment, construction near wetland areas, and the destruction of wetlands have significantly affected their ecological functioning. As a result, avian species tend to move away from these disturbed habitats and into human settlements in search of food and water, which increases the risks to their survival. Therefore, considering these facts, a study on avian biodiversity richness in six wetland areas of Jabalpur was conducted to assess the status of wetland birds. A total of 71 species of wetland birds were recorded, representing 17 families and 7 orders from six wetlands of the Narmada Valley. Ciconiiformes (20 species) was the largest order, comprising three families: Ardeidae, Ciconiidae and Threskiornithidae, followed by Coraciiformes and Anseriformes. Regarding residency status, the wetland-dependent bird species include. 23 Partial migrant (RM), 14 Migrant (M) and 34-Resident (R).

Keywords: Avian biodiversity; wetland; Narmada River; Ciconiiformes

Introduction:

India's biodiversity is remarkably enriched by the vast diversity of class Aves, making the country one of the most important regions for bird life in the world. The Indian subcontinent, with its extensive coastline stretching roughly 8,780 km, supports a wide range of coastal habitats, from mangroves and estuaries to sandy beaches and rocky shores. In addition to this long coastline, India is dotted with numerous wetlands. Wetlands are important natural resources and ecosystems in nature, that play an important role in maintaining ecological balance, hence they are also called "the kidneys of the Earth" (Paul, A. K., 2000 and Holland, M. M., 1996). It is also often called as biodiversity "hotspots" (Reid, *et al.* 2005). It is comprised of the most creative flora and fauna with a wide array of goods and services. These ecosystems serve as life support in many ways and provide unique habitat for a variety of avifauna including migratory birds for food and shelter. It also supports avian diversity in many ways and help to maintain dependent numerous species of flora as well as fauna. A study done by Rajput *et al.* (2021) in the district of Alirajpur along the banks of Narmada River also encases similar work. Thus, the necessity to study species of avifauna in wetlands of Jabalpur district elevates.

As human population is expanding in India and natural habitats of fauna is shrinking due to which people and animals increasingly come in conflict over living space and food. But, in recent years, wildlife is under threat due to variety of factors like human activities, deforestation, fragmentation of forests, landscape conversion for agriculture fields and human settlement, poaching of wild animals, mining, dams and interference of human. Shrinking of areas of wetland have been seen affecting its functioning. Large forest tracts have been degraded and fragmented resulting in poor food, water and cover. Avian biodiversity tends to move out from such disturbed forests in human settlement in search of food and water, causing damage to its life. These activities not only destroy the habitat of avian fauna but also lead to direct confrontation between wildlife and humans. A high diversity of bird species is often a strong indicator of a healthy and well-balanced ecosystem. Rich avian fauna suggests that the habitat provides ample food resources, suitable nesting sites, and stable environmental conditions capable of supporting a wide range of ecological niches. Such diversity also implies that the area is relatively free from major pollutants or disturbances, as many bird species are highly sensitive to changes in air, water, and habitat quality. When multiple species can coexist and

thrive, it reflects that the ecosystem has intact food webs, good vegetation cover, and minimal ecological stress (Gregory and van Strien, 2010).

Hunting and poaching of waterfowl and other animals prevalent in many parts of the country mainly threaten wetland faunal species. It is estimated that about 50% of the duck visiting the Manjhaur chaur near the Bihar-Bengal border are poached by duck trappers. Poachers kill about 15,000- 20,000 waterfowl each year in Chilka lake, Orissa. Due to which wetland dependent species have greatly depleted the wild populations (Ramchandra *et al.*, 2001).

The major objectives of the research were to conduct survey on the wetland biodiversity richness, as wetland harbored numerous species of bird which are directly or indirectly dependent upon and prepare strategy for wetland health management. Narmada valley in Jabalpur encompasses number of wetlands in Madhya Pradesh which serve as ideal habitat for dependent species. Therefore, looking to these facts the research on avian biodiversity richness in wetland areas of Jabalpur was done to know the status of wetland birds and prepare a check list for their sustainable conservation.

Material And Methods:**Study area**

The present research was done on the avian biodiversity of wetlands of Jabalpur region was carried out. Geographically, Jabalpur city is situated in the Mahakoshal region located at the center of India in the state of Madhya Pradesh having 23.1815° N latitude, 79.9864° E longitude (Figure. No.1). Six wetland areas were studied to know status of wetland biodiversity viz. Balsagar lake, Gangasagar Lake, Gwarighat (Narmada River bank), Mahanadda lake, Sangram sagar lake and Ranital Lake ((Figure. No. 2 and 3).

Survey and data collection

Surveys were made mostly in the early morning and evening hours of the day using (Olympus 10 x 50) binoculars and recorded shown in the Figure. No. 5 and 6. Standard avifaunal guides such as Grimmet *et al.* (1998) and Ali, S. (2002) were referred for identification of species, nomenclature and taxonomic position. The conservation status of the bird species was assessed according to the WPA, 1972 and IUCN guidelines mentioned in the literature. Species richness of aquatic bird was determined as per method prescribed by Kumar and Gupta (2009).

The observations on wetland bird biodiversity were made by field observation method (Bibby *et al.*, 1998) and a check list of birds is prepared. Arrangements of the species with common name in the Table No.01 are as per (Ali, 2002). Abundance of the bird species was reported

on the basis of species encountered in the study area. Abundance of birds was classified as: VC- Very Common (Seen very commonly in most of the study areas); C- Common (Seen commonly in the study areas); NR-

Not Rare (Seen many times but not common); RA- Rare (Seen only once or twice). Conservation status as per IUCN is categorized as VU- Vulnerable; LC-least concerned; NT- Near threatened and as per WP

Figure No. 1: Location map of Jabalpur in M.P., India

Figure No. 2 : Map of wetlands of Jabalpur

Index-1- Rani Talab; 2-Balsagar Talab; 3- Gangasagar Talab; 4- Mahanadda Talab; 5- Sagramsagar Talab and 6 -Gwarighat (Narmada River Bank)

Figure No. 3 : Six wetlands of Jabalpur

Ranital Talab, Jabalpur

Balsagar Talab, Jabalpur

Gangasagar Talab, Jabalpur

Mahanadda Talab, Jabalpur

Sangramsagar Talab, Jabalpur

Gwarighat, Jabalpur

Figure No. 4: Field survey on the biodiversity richness

Figure No. 5: Remote Health Monitoring of wetland dependent species

A (1972) - ** Birds with migratory populatio

Result And Discussion

A total of 71 species of wetland birds were recorded (Table 1 and Fig. 7). These comprised 17 families and seven (7) orders documented from six wetlands of Narmada Valley. The order Ciconiiformes (20) was the largest, represented by three families: Ardeidae, Ciconiidae and Threskiornithidae, followed by Coraciiformes and Anseriformes. Among the families, Ardeidae was the richest, with 17 species found in the different surveyed lakes, followed by Anatidae with 14 species and Motacillidae with 13 species. Five families: Podicipedidae, Rostratulidae, Recurvirostridae, Burhinidae, Glareolidae and Laridae, were each represented by single species.

The previous workers like Balapure *et al.* (2012) reported 63 bird species were recorded from Barna reservoir of Narmada basin belonging to 12 families and 7 orders. Family Anatidae was found to be the most dominant family represented by 16 species followed by Ardeidae with 9 species and Charadriidae with 8 species whereas Talmale *et al.* (2012) 173 bird species from Singhori Wildlife Sanctuary, Raisen District shown that order Ciconiiformes and Anseriformes was very rich with 17 and 14 species respectively. Dube *et al.* (2017) reported 46 species of birds belonging to 13 orders, 18 families avian faunal diversity in gun carriage factory estate area Jabalpur district, Madhya Pradesh in which order Ciconiiformes was very rich in that area followed Galliformes and Columbiformes.

Table No. 01: Checklist of birds in the wetlands of Jabalpur

S. No.	Order/Family/Scientific Name	Common Name	Residential Status	Abundance	Conservation Status	
					IUCN	WPA 1972
	Order : Podicipediformes Family : Podicipedidae					
1	<i>Tachybaptus ruficollis</i>	Little Grebe	R	NR	LC	Sch – II
	Order : Pelecaniformes Family : Phalacrocoracidae					
2	<i>Phalacrocorax niger</i>	Little Cormorant	R	VC	LC	Sch – II
3	<i>Phalacrocorax fuscicollis</i>	Indian Shag	R	C	LC	Sch – II
4	<i>Phalacrocorax carbo</i>	Great Cormorant	PM	C	LC	Sch – II
5	<i>Anhinga melanogaster</i>	Darter	PM	C	LC	Sch – II
	Order : Ciconiiformes Family : Ardeidae					
6	<i>Egretta garzetta</i>	Little Egret	R	VC	LC	Sch – II
7	<i>Ardea cinerea</i>	Grey Heron	R	C	LC	Sch – II
8	<i>Ardea purpurea</i>	Purple Heron	R	NR	LC	Sch – II
9	<i>Ardea alba</i>	Large Egret	R	C	LC	Sch – II
10	<i>Ardea intermedia</i>	Median Egret	R	C	LC	Sch – II
11	<i>Bubulcus ibis</i>	Cattle Egret	R	VC	LC	Sch – II
12	<i>Ardeola grayii</i>	Indian Pond-Heron	R	VC	LC	Sch – II
13	<i>Butorides striata</i>	Green Backed Heron	R	RA	LC	Sch – II
14	<i>Nycticorax nycticorax</i>	Black –crowned Night Heron	R	C	LC	Sch – II
15	<i>Ixobrychus cinnamomeus</i>	Chestnut Bittern	PM	NR	LC	Sch – II
16	<i>Ixobrychus sinensis</i>	Yellow Bittern	R	C	LC	Sch – II
17	<i>Ixobrychus flavicollis</i>	Black Bittern	R	C	LC	Sch – II
	Family : Ciconiidae					
18	<i>Mycteria leucocephala</i>	Painted Stork	PM	C	LC	Sch – II
19	<i>Anastomus oscitans</i>	Asian Openbill-Stork	PM	C	LC	Sch – II
20	<i>Ciconia nigra</i>	Black Stork	M	NR	LC	Sch – II
21	<i>Ciconia episcopus</i>	White-necked Stork	R	VC	NT	Sch – II
22	<i>Leptoptilos javanicus</i>	Lesser Adjutant-Stork	PM	NR	NT	Sch – II
	Family : Threskiornithidae					
23	<i>Plegadis falcinellus</i>	Glossy Ibis	PM	NR	LC	Sch – II
24	<i>Threskiornis melanocephalus</i>	Oriental White Ibis	R	C	NT	Sch – II

25	<i>Pseudibis papillosa</i>	Red-naped Ibis	R	C	LC	Sch – II
	Order : Anseriformes Family : Anatidae					
26	<i>Anser indicus</i>	Bar-headed Goose	M	C	LC	Sch – II
27	<i>Tadorna ferruginea</i>	Ruddy Shelduck	M	VC	LC	Sch – II
28	<i>Sarkidiornis melanotos</i>	Comb Duck	PM	C	LC	Sch – II
29	<i>Nettapus coromandelianus</i>	Cotton Pygmy Goose	M	C	LC	Sch – II
30	<i>Anas platyrhynchos</i>	Mallard	R	NR	LC	Sch – II
31	<i>Anas poecilorhyncha</i>	Spot-billed Duck	PM	NR	LC	Sch – II
32	<i>Spatula clypeata</i>	Northern Shoveler	M	C	LC	Sch – II
33	<i>Anas acuta</i>	Northern Pintail	M	C	LC	Sch – II
34	<i>Spatula querquedula</i>	Garganey	M	C	LC	Sch – II
35	<i>Anas crecca</i>	Common Teal	M	C	LC	Sch – II
36	<i>Netta rufina</i>	Red-crested Pochard	M	NR	LC	Sch – II
37	<i>Aythya ferina</i>	Common Pochard	M	NR	VU	Sch – II
38	<i>Aythya fuligula</i>	Tufted Pochard	M	NR	LC	Sch – II
	Order : Gruiformes Family : Rallidae					
39	<i>Amaurornis phoenicurus</i>	White-breasted Waterhen	R	C	LC	Sch – II
40	<i>Porphyrio poliocephalus</i>	Purple Moorhen	R	C	LC	Sch – II
41	<i>Fulica atra</i>	Common Coot	R	C	LC	Sch – II
42	Order : Charadriiformes Family : Jacanidae					
43	<i>Hydrophasianus chirurgus</i>	Pheasant-tailed Jacana	R	C	LC	Sch – II
44	<i>Metopidius indicus</i>	Bronze-winged Jacana	R	C	LC	Sch – II
	Family : Rostratulidae					
45	<i>Rostratula benghalensis</i>	Greater Painted-Snipe	PM	C	LC	Sch – II
	Family : Charadriidae					
46	<i>Charadrius dubius</i>	Little Ringed Plover	R	C	LC	Sch – II
47	<i>Vanellus malabaricus</i>	Yellow-wattled Lapwing	R	RA	LC	Sch – II
48	<i>Vanellus indicus</i>	Red-wattled Lapwing	R	VC	LC	Sch – II
	Family : Scolopacidae					
49	<i>Gallinago stenura</i>	Pintail Snipe	M	NR	LC	Sch – II
50	<i>Gallinago gallinago</i>	Common Snipe	PM	NR	LC	Sch – II
51	<i>Tringa glareola</i>	Wood Sandpiper	M	C	LC	Sch – II
	Family : Recurvirostridae					
52	<i>Himantopus himantopus</i>	Black-winged Stilt	PM	C	LC	Sch – II
	Family : Burhinidae					
53	<i>Burhinus indicus</i>	Indian Thick-knee	PM	NR	LC	Sch – II
	Family : Glareolidae					
54	<i>Glareola lactea</i>	Small Pratincole	PM	C	LC	Sch – II

	Family : Laridae					
55	<i>Sterna aurantia</i>	River Tern	R	C	VU	Sch – II
	Order : Coraciiformes					
	Family : Alcedinidae					
56	<i>Alcedo atthis</i>	Small Blue Kingfisher	R	VC	LC	Sch – II
57	<i>Halcyon smyrnensis</i>	White breasted Kingfisher	R	VC	LC	Sch – II
58	<i>Ceryle rudis</i>	Lesser Pied Kingfisher	R	C	LC	Sch – II
	Family : Motacillidae					
59	<i>Dendronanthus indicus</i>	Forest Wagtail	PM	RA	LC	Sch – II
60	<i>Motacilla alba</i>	White Wagtail	PM	C	LC	Sch – II
61	<i>Motacilla maderaspatensis</i>	Large Pied Wagtail	R	C	LC	Sch – II
62	<i>Motacilla flava</i>	Yellow Wagtail	PM	C	LC	Sch – II
63	<i>Motacilla cinerea</i>	Grey Wagtail	M	C	LC	
64	<i>Anthus rufulus</i>	Paddyfield Pipit	R	NR	LC	Sch – II
65	<i>Anthus trivialis</i>	Eurasian Tree Pipit	PM	C	LC	Sch – II
66	<i>Motacilla citreola</i>	Citrine Wagtail	PM	C	LC	Sch – II
67	<i>Anthus campestris</i>	Tawny Pipit	PM	NR	LC	Sch – II
68	<i>Anthus godlewskii</i>	Blyths Pipit	PM	NR	LC	Sch – II
69	<i>Anthus similis</i>	Brown Rock Pipit	PM	NR	LC	Sch – II
70	<i>Anthus hodgsoni</i>	Oriental Tree Pipit	PM	NR	LC	Sch – II
71	<i>Anthus roseatus</i>	Rosy Pipit	R	C	LC	Sch – II

R- Resident, PM- Partial migratory, M- Migratory; RA- Rare, NR- Not Rare, C- Common, VC- Very Common; LC- Least Concern, V- Vulnerable, NT- Near Threatened; IUCN - International Union for Conservation of Nature; WPA- Wildlife Protection Act, Sch II- Schedule II

Figure No. 6 : Wetland bird diversity in Jabalpur, M.P.

White-breasted waterhen

Great cormorant

Indian pond heron

Bronze-winged jacana

Indian shag

Black crown night heron

Wetland bird diversity in Jabalpur, M.P.

White breasted kingfisher

Lesser pied kingfisher

Small blue kingfisher

Marsh sandpiper

White necked stork

Asian openbill stork

Wetland bird diversity in Jabalpur, M.P.

Lesser adjutant stork

Black ibis

Oriental white ibis

Cattle egret

Little stint

White wagtail

Wetland bird diversity in Jabalpur, M.P.

Little egret

Painted stork

Black-winged stilt

Median egret

Chestnut bittern

Common moorhen

Wetland bird diversity in Jabalpur, M.P.

Cotton pygmy goose

Little cormorant

Large egret

Lesser whistling duck

Pheasant tailed jacana

Red wattled lapwing

Wetland bird diversity in Jabalpur, M.P.

Purple headed swamphen

Purple heron

Grey heron

Ruddy shelduck

Bank myna

Baya weaver

Fig. 7: Order-wise species diversity of wetland birds

R – Resident , RM – Partial migrant, M - Migrant

Fig. 8 - Number of species based on residential status

Conclusion

The study recorded 71 wetland bird species belonging to 17 families and 7 orders, demonstrating the productivity and ecological importance of these wetland habitats. The dominance of families like Ardeidae, Anatidae, and Motacillidae suggests that these habitats provide suitable conditions for wetland-dependent species, including ducks, and wading birds.

However, the long-term viability of these bird groups is seriously threatened by growing anthropogenic pressures such as habitat fragmentation, urban growth, poaching, pollution, and shrinkage of wetlands. Similar trends of deteriorating wetland health and faunal diversity have been in previous studies from the Narmada watershed and adjacent regions. The findings of the study highlight the urgent need for wetland conservation, safeguarding important bird habitats, regulation of human activity, and strict enforcement of the Wildlife Protection Act of 1972. To safeguard avian diversity, conservation efforts must incorporate sustainable wetland management techniques, habitat restoration, community awareness, and regular ecological monitoring. Overall, this study provides a thorough inventory of Jabalpur's wetland birds species and serves as a baseline reference for future ecological assessments, policy planning, and biodiversity conservation initiatives in the region.

Competing Interests

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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